

1. Have any data been collected for this study already?

No data has been collected.

2. What's the main question being asked or hypothesis being tested in this study?

This study investigates whether 3D Gaussian Splatting (3DGS) is perceived as an acceptable and visually plausible representation method for interactive AR-HMD object tasks compared to photogrammetry-based reconstructions. Participants will complete a task in which they can touch, move, and throw a represented object toward other represented objects, interact with the objects, and place them on a table in a specified order. The study uses a mixed design with table representation as a between-subjects factor, either a real physical table or a reconstructed 3DGS table, and object representation type as a within-subjects factor, comparing 3DGS-based and photogrammetry-based object representations across three object types.

RQ1: To what extent are 3DGS-based object representations accepted and preferred compared to photogrammetry-based object representations in an interactive AR-HMD task?

H1: Participants will show a systematic preference between 3DGS-based and photogrammetry-based object representations, with an expected preference toward 3DGS.

RQ2: Do object characteristics influence perceived differences between 3DGS and photogrammetry?

H2: The perceived advantage of 3DGS will be larger for objects that are difficult for photogrammetry to reconstruct, such as smooth, low-texture, reflective, or geometrically ambiguous objects.

RQ3: Does the table context influence scene plausibility and object-focused interaction ratings?

H3: Participants in the reconstructed 3DGS table condition will report lower table-specific physical presence than participants in the real table condition. However, table representation is expected to affect overall scene plausibility more strongly than object-focused representation preference.

3. Describe the key dependent variable(s) specifying how they will be measured.

The primary dependent variable is behavioral preference for the object representation type, measured as participants' choices between a 3DGS-based representation and a photogrammetry-based representation during the AR task.

In each of the three trials, participants encounter two object roles: a throwable object and a target object. For both roles, participants can inspect, touch, move, and interact with the available representations before making their choice. Participants first select which representation of the throwable object they want to use. They then throw this object toward one of the target object representations. The selected representation is recorded in the prototype for both the throwable object and the target object.

Each participant can therefore provide up to six behavioral representation choices: three choices for the throwable object and three choices for the target objects.

For the primary analysis, an overall participant-level majority preference will be computed across all valid behavioral choices. Participants will be classified as preferring 3DGS if they select the 3DGS representation in more than half of their valid choices, and as preferring photogrammetry if they select the photogrammetry representation in more than half of their valid choices. Participants with an equal number of 3DGS and photogrammetry choices will be classified as having no behavioral majority preference and reported separately.

Secondary analyses will examine representation choices separately for the throwable object and target object roles to determine whether representation preference differs depending on how the object is used during the task.

4. How many and which conditions will participants be assigned to?

Participants will be assigned to one of two between-subjects table conditions: a real physical table condition or a reconstructed 3DGS table condition.

Within each table condition, all participants will complete three trials.

Each participant can make up to six representation choices in total: three choices for the throwable object and three choices for the target objects.

The study follows a mixed design:

2 table conditions between subjects: real physical table vs. reconstructed 3DGS table

× 2 object representation types within subjects: 3DGS vs. photogrammetry

× 3 object within subjects: Object A, Object B, Object C.

Before the AR task, all participants will briefly see the physical study setup, including the table and the physical objects placed on it, while completing the demographic questionnaire. The objects will not be arranged in the final target order. This provides an initial real-world reference of the setup without explicitly drawing attention to the later table condition.

5. Specify exactly which analyses you will conduct to examine the main question/hypothesis.

To examine the main hypothesis, we will test whether participants show a systematic behavioral preference for 3DGS-based or photogrammetry-based object representations. For the primary analysis, choices will be aggregated at the participant level and classified by majority preference. Participants will be classified as preferring 3DGS if they select 3DGS in more than half of their valid choices, and as preferring photogrammetry if they select photogrammetry in more than half of their valid choices. Participants with an equal number of choices for both representations will be classified as showing no majority preference, reported separately, and excluded from the binary binomial test.

The primary hypothesis will be tested using a two-sided exact binomial test, equivalent to an exact sign test, against chance level $p=.50$, with $\alpha=.05$. We will report the number and proportion of participants preferring 3DGS among those with a clear majority preference, the exact p-value, and the corresponding 95% confidence interval.

To preserve information about preference strength, we will additionally compute the proportion of 3DGS choices for each participant, ranging from 0 to 1. This participant-level 3DGS choice proportion will be tested against .50 using a Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Effect sizes will be reported as rank-biserial correlations. Following Cohen's conventional benchmarks for correlation-type effect sizes, values of approximately .10, .30, and .50 will be interpreted as small, medium, and large effects, respectively. Participants with a proportion of exactly .50 will be included in descriptive statistics but will not contribute to the Wilcoxon test statistic. We will report descriptive statistics and the distribution of participant-level 3DGS choice proportions, including the number of participants with a proportion equal to .50.

Additional planned analyses will examine questionnaire-based pairwise ratings using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests against the neutral midpoint, with Holm correction for multiple comparisons. Table-specific ratings will be compared between the real table and reconstructed 3DGS table conditions using two-sided Mann-Whitney U tests, as these ratings are obtained from independent participant groups. Given the small group sizes, exact p-values will be used where available. For these comparisons, we will report descriptive statistics for each group and rank-biserial correlation as an effect size.

Standardized questionnaire scores will be analyzed descriptively. Think-aloud feedback will be summarized qualitatively to contextualize the quantitative findings.

6. Describe exactly how outliers will be defined and handled, and your precise rule(s) for excluding observations.

No statistical outliers will be removed from questionnaire-based or behavioral measures. Participants will only be excluded from the main analysis if technical failures prevent valid data capture or result in missing behavioral choice data required for the primary dependent variable. Missing questionnaire responses will not be imputed and will be treated as missing data.

7. How many observations will be collected or what will determine sample size?

We plan to recruit 20 participants. The sample size was determined using an a priori power analysis in G*Power for a two-sided exact binomial test against chance level $p_0 = .50$, with $\alpha = .05$, power $1 - \beta = .80$, and an expected large preference effect of $g = .30$, corresponding to an expected preference rate of $p_1 = .80$. This analysis indicated a required sample size of 20 participants.

Therefore, the study is powered to detect a large behavioral preference effect in the primary analysis. Smaller effects, as well as effects of the between-subjects table condition, will be interpreted descriptively and exploratorily due to the limited sample size.

8. Anything else you would like to pre-register?

No.